

Thermal Analysis of Ferroelectric Transition in Potassium Ferrocyanide Trihydrate

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Heat capacity of anhydrous potassium ferrocyanide, $K_4Fe(CN)_6$, was determined in the temperature range 80-300 K by isothermal calorimetry. Absence of anomalous behaviour around 248 K, the ferroelectric Curie point of potassium ferrocyanide trihydrate, $K_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 3H_2O$, indicated that hydrogen bonded water dipoles play a pivotal role in the ferroelectric behaviour of the hydrated salt. Using a corresponding states argument, the data on the anhydrous compound have been employed to estimate the enthalpy and entropy of the transition. The respective values were found to be 195 cal./mole and 0.81 cal./mole deg.

FERROELECTRICITY has gained considerable importance in recent years due to the fact that it poses several intriguing problems in solid state physics and chemistry and also because some of the ferroelectric crystals found immediate applications like electromechanical transducers, condenser materials, etc. Potassium ferrocyanide trihydrate, $K_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 3H_2O$, a common laboratory reagent, is found¹ to exhibit ferroelectric \rightarrow paraelectric transition around 248 K. From proton magnetic resonance and infrared absorption studies, Blinc *et al*² considered that the ferroelectric behaviour may be associated with the ordering of the hydrogen-bonded water molecules. Nuclear magnetic resonance and X-ray studies by Kiriyama *et al*³ also indicate that some mode change of the rotational motion of water molecules is closely connected with the ferroelectric transition. Heat capacity measurements by Nakagawa

*et al*⁴ revealed a hump around the Curie temperature T_c . Hence corresponding thermal studies of anhydrous potassium ferrocyanide, $K_4Fe(CN)_6$, were undertaken in the temperature range 80-300 K, with a view (i) to throwing more light on the role played by water dipoles in the ferroelectric behaviour of $K_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 3H_2O$, briefly referred to as KFCT, (ii) to estimating the enthalpy and entropy associated with the transition, and (iii) to determining the thermodynamic functions, such as entropy, enthalpy and Gibbs free energy, of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$, hereinafter referred to as KFC.

Experimental

The sample of KFC for calorimetric investigation was prepared by the method employed by Loftfield and Swift⁵. The constructional and operational details of the low temperature calorimeter have been described

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previously⁶. The experimental C_p data have been presented graphically in Fig. 1. The scatter of the C_p values from their own mean is about 1-1.5%.

Results and discussion

It will be seen from Fig. 1 that no anomaly in C_p of KFC is detected in the entire temperature range of measurements. This indicates that ferroelectricity of KFCT may be associated with the ordering of the water dipoles which, as NMR studies⁸ indicated, oscillate about their mean position below T_c , while above it, rotate freely. If this be the case, then the entropy of transition should be about $R \ln 2 = 1.38$ cal./mole deg.

Enthalpy and entropy of transition

It is essential that lattice heat capacity be estimated first with a degree of accuracy. For that purpose the following assumptions were made :

i) The lattice and anomalous contributions to C_p are additive and that electronic C_p is negligible at the high temperatures (~ 250 K) involved.

ii) Vibrational contributions to heat capacity and entropy of KFCT and KFC obey a law of corresponding states.

iii) The transition begins at 233 K and completes at 273 K.

The details of the method of estimation of lattice heat capacity were similar to those described by Stout and Catalano⁷. The scaling factor $\tau = (C_p \text{ of KFCT}) / (C_p \text{ of KFC})$, calculated by matching C_p values at 233 and 273 K respectively, was found to be 2.15. C_p of KFC was scaled up accordingly, which was then presumed to represent the lattice C_p of KFCT. Anomalous contribution, which was obtained by subtracting lattice heat capacity from the measured totals of KFCT, is shown in Fig. 1. The following values were obtained :

$$\Delta H = 195 \text{ cal./mole}$$

$$\Delta S = 0.81 \text{ cal./mole deg}$$

Since the entropy of transition is close to $R \ln 2$, it supports the conclusion reached from infrared and resonance studies that dynamical orientational ordering of water dipoles may be associated with the ferroelectric behaviour of KFCT.

Thermodynamic properties of potassium ferrocyanide

$$\text{A Debye-Einstein function } D \left(\frac{50}{T} \right) + 4E \left(\frac{130}{T} \right)$$

+ $6E \left(\frac{285}{T} \right)$ was fitted to the experimental heat capacity data of KFC to within $\pm 1\%$ and then employed to evaluate entropy, enthalpy and free energy between 80-300 K. The respective values at a few selected temperatures are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF ANHYDROUS POTASSIUM FERROCYANIDE

T/K	C_p° cal./mol K	(1 cal = 4.184 J) $S^\circ - S_0^\circ$ cal./mol K	$H^\circ - H_0^\circ$ cal./mol	$-(G^\circ - H_0^\circ)/T$ cal./mol K
80	38.3	(29.15)*	(1428)*	(11.30)*
100	41.6	38.08	2227	15.81
150	54.9	57.10	4593	26.48
200	68.9	74.90	7697	36.40
250	73.7	91.15	11300	45.95
300	76.2	104.60	15030	54.55
(298.15)**	(76.0)**	(104.2)**	(14890)*	(54.19)**

* Extrapolated values

** Interpolated values

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